

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.433 Max: 62.609	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1454 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic			
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1963-66	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:			
DEFINITION threshold worked stone				Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 0	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:		
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction		FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition						
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are				SOIL/MATRIX				
Anthropic		Geological		Organic				
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		
				clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive				
				Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft		Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)								
Northern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit			Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original			
Southern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit						
Western Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit broken on western edge						
Eastern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit						
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE								
Is equal to:				Is bound to (only for masonry):				
Is abutted by:				Abuts:				
Is covered by: 0				Covers: 1001 and soil				
Is cut by:				Cuts:				
Is filled by:				Fills:				
OBSERVATIONS not tied to the soil, most likely moved by previous excavation, but possible it was near the original situ								
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: on the southern extent of Area B, located to the west of center. nearly directly south of SU 1448 Shape: originally rectangular, 2 sides now are well preserved now irregular								
For layers complete this section:								
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):								
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):								
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):								
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)								
For cuts complete this section:				Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):				
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight								
Cut sides <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping								
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular								
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded								
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded								
Observations:								

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: *N-S*

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (block) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing: —

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations: Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type —

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

L=97cm W=33cm H=12cm

Description:

*worked stone block,
possibly a threshold
stone, has been
poorly eroded*

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

worked block which may have been used as a threshold. Most likely not in original situ, but after previous excavations may have been positioned near the original context. The block is nearly in line with wall 1448 and may have once been a part of this wall.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by *S. Jon*

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PDFd by *ELR*

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on